

REALIZING THE RIGHTS OF CHILD UNDER THE NIGERIAN CHILD'S RIGHTS ACT, 2003: AN EXPLORATORY CRITIQUE.

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ABSTRACT

Nigeria, a state party, domesticated the UNCRC by enacting the Nigerian Child rights Act 2003. The Act provides for the rights of the children classified into four broad ways viz; the rights of the child to protection, participation, survival and development. However, despite this protection of the rights of child under the Act, realizing some of these rights in practical terms by Nigeria children may be hindered by certain prevailing challenges. Among other factors considered to have contributed to the near impotency of the Act, is the socio- cultural, religious, legal and economic prevalence in Nigeria. This paper focuses on the rights of child under the Child Rights Act, 2003, and explores the extent to which the cultural, religious, legal and economic prevalence in Nigeria, affect the realisations of the rights of child under the Nigeria Child Rights Act, 2003.

Keywords: Child's Rights, Critique, Legitimacy, Culture, Religion, Economic and legal.

1. INTRODUCTION.

It is beyond rhetoric that children are among the most vulnerable and powerless members of the society. Children are vulnerable for the fact that they owe their existence upon the actions and omission of the adults. The popular assumption, in time past Africa was that adults and in particular parents, have the best interest of the child at heart, therefore there is no need to necessarily think in terms of children's rights.¹ This is because families' attitude towards children in traditional African Society, generally is warm, exciting, positive and full of expectations for the future. Children were seen as the future of the families and the communities. In this regards mankind owes the children everything since its future depends on the children.²

In modern time, sadly, these aspirations seem to have been eroded by reasons such as socio economic hardship and other related modern vices resulting into what is regarded as child abuse. According to United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF); despite the rhetoric in the international and national community about the importance of Children's Rights, 'the rights, norms and principles involved are regularly ignored and seriously violated virtually throughout the world...on a scale...unmatched in the field of Human Rights implementation'.³

The non implementations and of course the vulnerability of child, makes the child to be susceptible to many challenges among which are; Child abuse which entails a child growing up under conditions, which threaten his physical and emotional survival.⁴ Child labour, which includes work by children under conditions harmful to their health usually for long hours and for very low wages,⁵ such work is destructive and exploitative.⁶ Sexual child abuse which includes taking advantage of a child's tender years by subjecting the child to engage in sexual activities.⁷ Child neglect which is seen as a deficit in meeting a child's basic needs. Child prostitution which is the commercial sexual exploitation of children⁸ in which a child performs the services of prostitution, for financial benefit,⁹ and lastly lack of education.¹⁰

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¹ I A Ayua et al, 'The Rights of Child in Nigeria. Lagos,' (1996) NIALS, p.31. Cited in E I Alemika, 'Legal frameworks for the Child Rights in Nigeria', (2010) 3(2), *Journal of public law and constitutional practice*, Faculty of law, university of Jos, p. 4.

² Kofi Anna Speech at the world children summit, (2002). <<http://www.unicef.org.modified17march2008>> accessed on 20th April, 2014.

³ UNICEF, 'Juvenile Justice Florence', (1998) *Innocenti Digest*, No. 3. <<http://www.unicef-irc.org/publications/pdf/digest3e.pdf>> accessed on 6th May, 2016.

⁴ E Joy and O Oyinye, 'Child Abuse and Neglect', (Published by: Women's Aid Collective (WACOL), Nigeria, 2002.) <http://books.google.com/books/about/child_abuse_and_neglect.html?_f6zraAAAAMAAJ> accessed on 15th June 2015.

⁵ K Basu, 'Child Labour: Causes, Consequence and Cure, with Remarks on International Labour Standards', (1999), 39(3), *Journal of Economic Literature*, pp. 1083-1119.

⁶ See M O Ojo, "Sociological Investigation of the determinant factors and the effects of Child Street Hawking in Nigeria: Agege, Lagos, under survey", (2013), 3(1) *International Journal of Asian Social Science*, pp. 114-137. <<http://www.aessweb.com/journal.php?id=5007>> accessed on the 10th of June, 2015.

⁷ E Joy and O Oyinye, 'Child Abuse and Neglect' pp. 14 – 23.

⁸ UNICEF, 'Juvenile Justice Florence'. p. 10.

⁹ P O Ebigbo, A profile of Child Trafficking in Nigeria, Enugu: Fourth Dimension Federal Ministry of Education Crisis: 'The State of the Nigerian Education System and the Agenda for Reform' (2006),

The idea that children have specific rights deserving protection and enforcement is not a new one. Since 1959 there have been a broad spectrum of laws¹¹ which were available for the protection of child rights both nationally and internationally. The prominent among the international laws is the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child, (UNCRC) 1989.¹² By becoming parties to these international treaties, State agree to be bound by its terms and to take all political, legal and administrative steps necessary to implement the core imperatives of the treaties as encapsulated in it Articles.¹³ In effect, this means that State parties have the obligation to take legislative steps, among others, to ensure that Children's Right as contained in the treaties are realized and implemented in the domestic systems.¹⁴ The Nigerian Government domesticated the UNCRC by enacting the Child's Rights Act, 2003.¹⁵ (Herein after refer to as the Act).

Despite the enactment of Nigerian Child's Rights Act, 2003, realizing some of these rights by Nigerian children is not without its own challenges of impracticability and for several years, Nigeria has been criticized for the human rights and children's rights violations perpetrated on her territory.¹⁶ Many factors are presumably accountable and identified by various studies, as to the non-realizations of rights by Nigerian children under the Act.¹⁷ Aside the factor that Nigeria is a pluralist state with multiple laws, norms and forum that co-exist to function as a legal system,¹⁸ there are the Socio - cultural, legal, religious and economic prevalence in Nigeria which were factors necessary to be considered for the practical realisations of some of the basic rights of child under the Child Rights Act, 2003.

It therefore becomes necessary, to appraise the rights of the child under the Nigerian Child's Rights Act, 2003 and explore the extent to which the cultural, religious, legal and economic prevalence in Nigeria affected the issues of child rights under the Act and perhaps makes recommendations towards ensuring practical realisation of child rights, thereby making 'the best interests of the child to be a primary consideration'¹⁹ in all matters concerning the child.

<http://www.ibe.unesco.org/National_Reports/ICE.../nigeria_NR08.pdf> accessed on 12th February 2013.

¹⁰ A Adeyemi, 'The UN Convention and OAU Charter on the Right and Welfare of the Child: Basic principles constraints and prospects of implementation in Nigeria'. (paper delivered at the 1995 National worship on child Right Monitoring held at Enugu 29th Nov. 1995). p. 19.

¹¹ Some of these laws include laws such as League of Nations Declaration of the Right of the Child, 1924; United Nations Declaration of the Rights of the Child, 1959; Declaration of the Rights and Welfare of the African Child, 1979 and The 1948 Universal Declaration of Human Rights.

¹² See The State of the World's Children, 'Celebrating 20 years of the Convention on the Rights of Child. United Nation Children's Fund'. Special Edition, November 2009. <http://www.unicef.org/publications>. Accessed on the 4th of April, 2015.

¹³ United Nations Convention on the Rights of Child (UNCRC). Article 4.

¹⁴ Information sheet, 'The Childs Right Act'. <http://www.unice.org/wcaro/WCRAO_Nigeria_Factsheets> p.2. Accessed on 4th of April 2015.

¹⁵ Nigerian Child's Rights Act, 2003, Act No. 26 of 2003.

¹⁶ OMCT: 'Report on the Human Rights Situation in Nigeria (Human Rights Committee)', Geneva, October 2002, p.3.

¹⁷ F Amagiya, 'Child Abuse: The Story of the Nigerian Child', Vanguard May 26, 2012.

<<http://www.vanguardngr.com>>. Accessed 17 June 2014.

¹⁸ As a federation, each component state in Nigeria under the Constitution is empowered to make laws i.e. federal government makes laws on all matter in the exclusive lists and share law making with the state on the concurrent list. Children are classified for legislation under the residual matter which is legislated by the states. The implication is that the various states can adopt or refuse to adopt any law enacted at the national level regarding children. See the 1999 Constitution of the federal republic of Nigeria section 4 and 2nd Schedule, Parts I and II.

¹⁹ See UNCRC, article 3 and Nigeria Child's Rights Act, s.1.

2. BACKGROUND TO THE ENACTMENT OF THE NIGERIAN CHILD'S RIGHT ACT 2003.

In 1996, Nigeria submitted its first Report on the Implementation of the UNCRC to the Committee on the Rights of the Child (CROC). The Committee recommended to Nigeria to domesticate the UNCRC to enable its full implementation under Nigerian law.²⁰ Prior to submission of her first report, there was a Bill on Children's rights in 1993, that did not see the light of the day during military government due to opposition from religious groups and traditionalists. This necessitate the setting up of a special committee primarily to "harmonize the Children's Bill with Nigerian religious and customary beliefs."²¹

In October 2002, in equal like manner, a bill purposely meant to provide for the rights and the responsibilities of children in Nigeria and for a renewed system of juvenile justice administration, was in Parliament rejected, because its contents were 'perceived as being contrary to religious values, traditions and culture.' The antagonist of the bill targeted the setting of 18 years as the minimum age for marriage and argues that it is inconsistent with 'religious and cultural traditions in various parts of the country'.²² Many sectors of the civil society in Nigeria as well as 'International and national Non-governmental organisation (NGOs)', were said to have criticized this decision and the legislator had to reconsider its decisions opposing the Child Rights Bill. In September 2003, the Bill was finally adopted,²³ notwithstanding the uproar and rejection of certain provisions by the religion and cultural proponent.²⁴

3. THE NIGERIAN CHILD'S RIGHTS ACT, 2003.

The Child rights Act, 2003 is a comprehensive embodiments of rights seeking to protect the rights of the Children in Nigeria. However, the rights as encapsulated in the Act are interchanging, therefore for clarity, ease of reference and to avoid repetitive analysis, these rights, are classified herein, into four broad ways namely; survival rights, development rights, participation rights and protection rights. Thus, the section of the paper examines the rights of Child under the Act in the direction of the above classifications vis -a-vis the part and sections of the Act.

²⁰ UNCRC, Concluding Observations of the Committee on the Rights of the Child: Nigeria, CRC/C/15/Add.61,30/10/96, § 26.

<[http://www.unhchr.ch/tbs/doc.nsf/\(Symbol\)/CRC.C.15.Add.61.En?OpenDocument](http://www.unhchr.ch/tbs/doc.nsf/(Symbol)/CRC.C.15.Add.61.En?OpenDocument)> accessed on 7th May 2015.

²¹ UNICEF, quoted in Integrated Regional Information Networks (IRIN), Nigeria: 'Focus on the challenge of enforcing children's rights, November 2002'. <<http://www.irinnews.org/print.asp?ReportID=30878>> accessed on 6 February 2015. See also OMCT/CLEEN, 'Rights of Child in Nigeria', Report on the implementation of the Convention on the rights of child by Nigeria for the Committee on the Rights of Child 38th Session - Geneva, January 2005, p. 6.

²² OMCT/CLEEN, 'Rights of Child in Nigeria', Report on the implementation of the Convention on the rights of child by Nigeria for the Committee on the Rights of Child 38th Session - Geneva, January 2005, pp. 5 - 6. <http://www.cleen.org/nigeria_ngo_report_OMCT.pdf Accessed on 11th September, 2016.

²³ Ibid. Note also that the 'Trafficking in Persons (prohibition) Law Enforcement and Administration Act' was passed into law on 14 July 2003. It is available on internet: <http://www.unicri.it/nigeria_law_trafficking.PDF>.

²⁴ Ibid

3.1 The best interest of the child.

Part 1, (Section 1-2) the Act provides that the best interest of the child shall be the paramount consideration in all actions to be taken by all concerned. Therefore, individual, public or private body, institutions or service, court of law, administrative or legislative authority shall adhere in their duties towards ensuring the best interest of the child. The Act further provides that necessary protection and care shall be given to the child for his/her well being, taking into account the rights and duties of the child's parents, legal guardians and other bodies that are legally responsible for the child.

3.2 Survival and Development Rights

Part II (Section 3-20) provides for the rights and responsibility of a child in Nigeria. It entrenches certain fundamental rights for children which includes; rights to survival and development, to a name, to freedom of association and peaceful assembly, to freedom of thought, conscience and religion, to private and family life, to freedom of movement, to freedom from discrimination, to dignity of the child, to leisure, recreation and cultural activities, to health and health care services, to parental care, protection and maintenance, to free, compulsory and universal primary education as well as encouragement of the child to attend and complete secondary education.

3.3 Protection Rights

Part III (Section 21-40) provides for the protection of the rights of the child through the prohibition of the child marriage, child betrothal, infliction of tattoos and skin marks, exposure to use, production, trafficking, use of children in any criminal activities, abduction and unlawful removal and transfer of a child from lawful custody, forced, exploitative or hazardous child labour, outlawry of employment of a child as domestic help outside their own home or family environment, buying, selling, hiring or otherwise dealing in children for the purpose of hawking, begging for alms, prostitution, unlawful sexual intercourse, other forms of sexual abuse and exploitation prejudicial to the welfare of the child.²⁵

The Act further prohibit recruitment of the children into the armed forces of Nigeria and importation of harmful publication which portray information such as the commission of crimes, act of violence, immoral and indecent representations which tends to corrupt a child.²⁶ The Act also preserves the continued application of all criminal law provisions securing the protection of the born or unborn child.²⁷

3.4 Further Protection and Participation Rights

Part IV (Section 41-49) provides for the additional protection through civil and welfare proceedings. Therefore, it contains provisions that enables assessment order to be secured in order to ascertain the state of the health or development of, or the way in which a child has been treated, with a view to enabling a determination as to whether the child is suffering or is likely to suffer significant harm. In this nexus, an order may be secured from the family court, by the appropriate authority, for emergency protection of the children where and when

²⁵ Nigeria Child's Rights Act Ss. 21 - 32

²⁶ Nigeria Child's Rights Act Ss. 33 - 35

²⁷ Nigeria Child's Rights Act S. 40

circumstance dictates.²⁸ Additional duties are equally imposed on the state government by the Act to safeguard and promote the welfare of any child in danger or suspected to be in danger of suffering significant harm within its jurisdiction.²⁹

Part V (Sections 50- 52) empowers the development of a child. Under this provisions police officers or any other authorized person are required to bring a child in need of care and protection before a court for corrective order, if there is a reasonable grounds to believe that the Child is an orphan or is deserted by relative, neglected, ill treated or battered by his/her parents, guarding or custodian, or if the child is found destitute, wandering, homeless, or the Child surviving parent is undergoing imprisonment, mentally unstable or otherwise severally handicapped; or found begging for alms, or in company of reputed/common thief or prostitute, or otherwise beyond parental control or exposed to moral danger or physical danger.³⁰

The Nigeria Child's Rights Act contains other provisions which includes; general care and supervision order.³¹ Use of scientific test to determine the paternity or maternity of a child.³² Possession of custody of children.³³ Guardianship, Wardship, Fostering and Adoption,³⁴ Establishment of the family court, child minding, day care centres and Allied homes,³⁵ Child Rights implementation committees,³⁶ and Miscellaneous matters.³⁷

With the provisions of the Child's Rights Act, 2003 considered above, it is beyond doubt that the welfare and responsibilities of children as well as those of government and institutions towards children are more defined. Equally, of immense benefit to the child from the Act is the unlimited scope of who may enforce the rights of the child. These rights may be enforced by a person who has parental responsibility for the child; by the state government or any other appropriate authority; by concerned citizens; by non-governmental organisations and civil societies; by government at all levels; by clubs and societies; by neighbourhood societies; by concerned neighbours; by educational institutions; by religious organizations; by political parties; by voluntary organizations and all such other stakeholders with concern about the welfare, growth and development of the Nigerian child.³⁸ The rationale behind the limitless nature of the scope of persons that are at liberty to enforce the rights of the Nigerian child is perhaps on the notion that the values of the society could only be promoted or bastardized by the youths having regards to the simple truth that Children are the future of any society or civilization.³⁹ The children's population constitutes a significant segment of Nigerian youths in this context.⁴⁰

²⁸ Nigeria Child's Rights Act 41 (1) (1 - 10)

²⁹ Nigeria Child's Rights Act Ss. 42 (1) (1 - 14) and s. 42.

³⁰ Nigeria Child's Rights Act s. 50 - 52

³¹ Nigeria Child's Rights Act, s. 53- 62.

³² Nigeria Child's Rights Act, s 63-67.

³³ Nigeria Child's Rights Act, s. 68-81.

³⁴ Nigeria Child's Rights Act, s. 82- 92.

³⁵ Nigeria Child's Rights Act, s. 149- 203.

³⁶ Nigeria Child's Rights Act, s. 260- 271.

³⁷ Nigeria Child's Rights Act, s. 272- 274.

³⁸ See the provisions of the Nigeria Child's Rights Act, 2003 generally.

³⁹ P Kunig, W Benedek & C Mahalu, 'Regional Protection of Human Rights by International law: The emerging African System', (Normer Verlagsgesellschaft, 1985), p. 89.

⁴⁰ See Demographic statistic bulletin 2015. A publication of demographic statistic division of the Nigeria bureau of statistic. Figure 1 therein, shows the projected population of Nigeria from 2006-2015. Available at <http://www.nigerianstat.gov.ng/library#content5-6>. Also according to the Demographics of Nigeria by

Summarily, the Act covers rights for the participation, protection, survival and development of every child in Nigeria. However, despite all these protections provided by the Act, realizing some of these rights by Nigeria children is of course, without its own peculiar challenges.

4. CRITIQUE OF THE NIGERIAN CHILD'S RIGHT ACT, 2003

This section of the paper examines the critique on the rights of Child under the Nigerian Child rights Act 2003. The tune at which analysis herein flows, is by way of exploring certain instance of the extent to which the cultural, religious, legal and economic prevalence in Nigeria affect the issues of child's right under the Act.

4.1 Cultural Critique.

The first point of call under this heading is examining the issue of who is a child under the Act vis – a – vis certain cultural practice.

The Child's Right Act defines a 'child as a person under the age of eighteen years.'⁴¹ It is therefore beyond contention, going by the above definitions, that a child is considered in the face of the Act as an individual that is meek and innocent and in dire needs of the protection of the parents and the law in order to survive and grow properly into a complete being.

In Nigeria, like other African society that evolves from traditional setting, the term 'child' does not yield to an easy definition as the provision of the law from the legal perspective above indicate. A child in African traditional setting is not subjected to a particular age or number.⁴² The common practice in most African communities from the cultural aspect is that a boy and a girl remains a child until initiated into age grade. There are different types of initiations rite from childhood to adulthood across various ethnic groups and culture in Nigeria.⁴³ Instances include the circumcision or initiations of a teenager (boy or girl) into some cult or family shrine as pre condition for marriage or taking of other responsibilities as practiced among the Igbo, Yoruba, Edo and Delta people in Nigeria.⁴⁴ Equally, other tribe, majorly the Plateau, Kogi and Benue, age grade farming competition were usually organised by the parent of an intended suitor, to lead his age grade and work on the intended farther in laws farms. This is regarded as proof that the person is no longer a child and ripe for marriage.⁴⁵

In some other communities, childhood terminates at the stage of puberty. These in most cases is determined by the appearance of pubic hairs in boys and breast or commencement of

Wikipedia, the proportion of Children below the age of 15 in 2010 was 44.0%, 53% was between the age of 15 and 65 years, while 2.7% was 65 years or older. See Wikipedia: 'The Demographics of Nigeria', <https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Demographics_of_Nigeria> Accessed on 9th November, 2016.

⁴¹ Nigeria Child's Rights Act, s. 277.

⁴² E.I Alemika, 'Legal frameworks for the Child Rights in Nigeria'. (2010), 3(2), *Journal of public law and constitutional practice*, Faculty of law, university of Jos. p. 4

⁴³ Ibid at pp. 4-5.

⁴⁴ Ibid at p. 5.

⁴⁵ This is similar to the Hausa Fulani tribe wherein the suitors will engage in beating of each other with his age grade without shedding tears. The essence is to attest to the proof that the suitor is no longer a child and ripe for marriage.

menstruation in girls.⁴⁶ According to Ayua, ‘a study conducted by the Nigerian Institute of Advanced Legal Studies to demarcate childhood from adulthood in Nigeria, over 48 % of parents responded that any person under the age of 20 years is a child. 14.3 % said any person under 30 years is a child, while 63% said any person who cannot provide means of living by himself or herself is by all standards a child.’⁴⁷ Therefore, it is safe to contend that, in Africa – Nigeria inclusive, the question of who a child is, are not measured by a particular number of years, as done by the Child Rights Act 2003 - pegging a child as any person under the age of 18.⁴⁸ Often, the combination of physical, psychological and emotional strength of individual plays an important role. The consequence of the above is that Parents and society at large may find it difficult to streamline these imbibed cultural notions with the Child rights Act positions.

Another right as guaranteed under the Act is the participation right of Children which include freedom of expression and the right to be heard which allows the child to participate and express himself freely.⁴⁹ However, under cultural practice in certain locality,⁵⁰ it would amount to frivolity and rudeness if the child freely expresses his or her opinion. In most African countries the child is not allowed to air his or her opinion, rather he takes instructions.⁵¹

It must be noted that the use of corporal punishment for the correction of the child is widespread and widely endorsed in Nigeria.⁵² Despite the fact that the Act frowns at corporal punishment, most parents’ cultural belief is that when a child does wrong, the best way to correct him or her is to flog or beat that child. Most parents rely on the popular saying that ‘*spare the rod and spoil the child*. This saying has its root in certain culture.⁵³ However some parents have abused their right to correct the child by going as far as inflicting serious injury just in the name of correcting the child thereby abusing the child.⁵⁴

Another instance of cultural constraints is on child labour. The Act categorically frowns at child labour.⁵⁵ However, under certain culture in Nigeria, there are beliefs that indulging a child in certain labour prepares the child for adult roles.⁵⁶ It is believed that this enables the child to learn a skill that will be useful and beneficial to him or her in the future. Therefore,

⁴⁶ It is important to note that the biological mode of development in each individual is different. Therefore, the age at which people develop physical attributes varies. Some develop rapidly while others have retarded growth; hence physical element of the body is a determining factor of adulthood.

⁴⁷ I A Ayua, et al, ‘*The Right of Child in Nigeria. Lagos*,’ p. 4

⁴⁸ Nigeria Child’s Rights Act, s. 277.

⁴⁹ Nigeria Child’s Rights Act, s. 215 (1) (a).

⁵⁰ A Twum-Danso, ‘Reciprocity, Respect and Responsibility: The 3Rs Underlying Parent–child Relationships in Ghana and the Implications for Children’s Rights’ (2009), 17 (3), *The International Journal of Children’s Rights*, 415–432. Also the Yoruba’s of western part of Nigeria cultural practice is a good example in this regard.

⁵¹ T Kiame, ‘The Convention on the Right of Child and the Cultural legitimacy of Child’s Rights in Africa: some reflection’, 5 *African Journal of Human Rights* 221- 238.

<http://reference.sabinet.co.za/nwulib.nwu.ac.za/webx/access/electronic_journals/ju_ahrlj/ju_ahrlj_v5_n2_a3.pdf> Accessed on 5 August, 2016.

⁵² OMCT/CLEEN, ‘Rights of Child in Nigeria’, Report on the implementation of the Convention on the rights of child by Nigeria for the Committee on the Rights of Child 38th Session - Geneva, January 2005. Pp.16 - 18

⁵³ Again the Yoruba’s places much emphasis on the issue of disciplining erring child to forestall the child becoming a nuisance to the society in the future.

⁵⁴ OMCT/CLEEN, ‘Rights of Child in Nigeria’, Report on the implementation of the Convention on the rights of child by Nigeria for the Committee on the Rights of Child 38th Session - Geneva, January 2005. p. 18.

⁵⁵ Nigeria Child’s Rights Act, s.30.

⁵⁶ The Yoruba culture for instance.

the delineating of certain labour by the adult on a child such as going to the farm to work and/or hawking wares as child abuse by the Act, seems not take into consideration the cultural belief of adults that indulge a child in such practice.

Equally, on cultural constraint is the issue of tattoos and skin mark.⁵⁷ The Act guarantees the rights of a child against tattoos and skin mark.⁵⁸ Various cultures in Nigeria still regard tribal marks as a mark of identity. Some parents from the royal lineage in the western part of Nigeria still indulge in the practice of skin mark or tribal mark as a mark of royal identity on their children.⁵⁹ Whereas the Act categorically state such practices as child abuse and provides punishment of fine or imprisonment for same.⁶⁰

4.2 Religious Critique.

Marriageable age is an issue of boiling concern under religion. This in a way has a link with cultural constraints on age already discussed above. However, the major issue under herein borders on the pegging of the age of a child as below 18 years.⁶¹ In other words, the Act condemns the marriage of an individual below the age of 18 years, notwithstanding that marriageable age under religion such as Islamic religion and certain cultural belief as practiced both in the southern and northern part of Nigerian varies and not necessarily pegged to eighteen years.⁶² Indeed, as earlier pointed out, the debate on this Marriageable age necessitated the prolong enactment of the Child Rights Act in 2003, nearly almost a decade after Nigeria ratification of the UNCRC. Even as at that, the provision of below 18 years as measure for who is a child⁶³ still find its way into the Child Rights Act 2003, despite opposition from religious and cultural proponents in Nigeria.⁶⁴

Another point worthy of note is the issue of adoption under the Act. The Act specifically provides for procedure for adoption. Under Islamic religion,⁶⁵ adoption is generally not allowed,⁶⁶ ostensibly because it disrupts the pattern of family relationships that Islamic law recognises and invests with legal rights and duties. In some societies, such as pre-Islamic

⁵⁷ Skin mark means any ethnic or ritual cuts on the skin which leaves permanent marks. See Nigeria Child's Rights Act, s.277 on interpretation.

⁵⁸ Nigeria Child's Rights Act, s. 24.

⁵⁹ The issue of Skin mark is not only restricted to the western part of Nigeria. In the Northern and Eastern part are instances where Skin mark or Tribal mark are being carried out. However, the use of tribal marks or skin mark is fading away. See Wikipedia: Yoruba Tribal marks. Available at https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/yoruba_tribal_marks Accessed on 9th November, 2016.

⁶⁰ Nigeria Child's Rights Act, s. 24 (2).

⁶¹ OMCT/CLEEN, 'Rights of Child in Nigeria', Report on the implementation of the Convention on the rights of child by Nigeria for the Committee on the Rights of Child 38th Session - Geneva, January 2005'. pp. 11.

⁶² Ibid at p. 12. See also discussion on background to the enactment of Nigerian child's rights Act 2003.

⁶³ Nigeria Child's Rights Act, s. 277.

⁶⁴ E Anaba, 'Why the Child Rights Bill Must Be Passed into Law', in *Vanguard Newspapers*, Nigeria, Friday 16 May 2003, p. 26. Cited in S O Akinwumi, 'Legal Impediments on the Practical Implementation of the Child Right Act 2003', (2009) *International Journal of Legal Information*, p.31.

⁶⁵ According to Islam in Nigeria by Wikipedia, 'Nigeria has one of the largest Muslim populations in west Africa, with the Pew Research centre estimating that it is between 48.5% in 2010'. See Wikipedia: 'Islam in Nigeria', <https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Islam_in_Nigeria> Accessed on 9th November, 2016.

⁶⁶ Abdl al Ati, *Islam in Focus*, (Riyadh: International Islamic Federation of Student Organisations, 1986), pp.192-193.

Arabia, adoption occurred hand in hand with certain corollary practices,⁶⁷ such as the right of a family to disclaim a member, or of a person to renounce his biological family, both of which were promoted by the possibility of being adopted into another family. Islamic law prohibits all these practices and demands that every person should maintain his or her natural identity.⁶⁸ These prohibition of adoption, however, does not prevent one person from taking the responsibility of raising the child of another, which is a meritorious deed in Islam, called *kafalah*,⁶⁹ widely practiced and could even become a duty. The finder of a foundling, for instance, is duty-bound to take care of it and raise it in the manner he or she would raise his or her own children.

Similarly, if natural parents are incapable of raising their child, the Islamic solution is not adoption. It is for Muslim society to assist them, in case they only require material help, or for the child to be placed with other parents who are as closely related to the child's natural family as possible. The new parents will not, under Islamic law, totally displace the natural parents but will perform their function as an act of personal charity or for compensation, according to the demands of each case.⁷⁰ These foregoing procedures of adoption under Islamic law sharply differs from the requirement under the Nigerian Child's rights Act, 2003.

4.3 Economic Critique.

These consist of the governmental and individual constraints as regards operation of the Act protecting the rights of child. For example, the right of the child to reside with and be brought up by one's parents may not be feasible in a situation where the family is faced with adverse economic hardship amounting to poverty. In such a case, the child may either be sent to immediate or distant relation as domestic help, childminder, or may even be forced to embark on child labour as an alternative source of improving the family meagre income. Again, the right of fair hearing,⁷¹ guaranteed under the Act may not be feasible for a child from a poor family, who will be deprived of legal representation for the inability of non-availability of fund to pay such representation. On the other hand, government may lack the fund to implement the right guaranteed in the instruments. Even where such funds are available, these may be ploughed into those needs on their priority lists.

Also the rights to compulsory primary education of children guaranteed under the Act may not be equally feasible for a child from poor home. Many children do not attend school because their labour is needed to either help at home or to bring additional income into the family. Many families cannot afford the associated costs of sending their children to school such as uniforms and textbooks. For others, the distance to the nearest school is a major hindrance. Even when children enrol in schools, many do not complete the primary cycle. According to Akinwumi Silas,⁷² 30% of pupils drop out of primary school and only 54%

⁶⁷ Abdl al Ati, *Family structure in Islam*, (Indianapolis, IN: American Trust Publications' 1982, 189), p.24.

⁶⁸ Holy Qur'an 33: 4-6. See also G Van Bueren, *The international law on the rights of the child*, (Dordrecht, Martinus Nijhoff Publishers, London, 1995), p.95.

⁶⁹ The term *kafalah* has its roots in the Islamic law of obligations. It permits a person to enter into a contract committing himself/herself to certain undertakings in favour of another person provided that person has a material or moral interest in such undertaking. Even though not on the same legal plane as the Western idea of adoption, it is becoming rampant in transboundary child adoptions even in the Islamic world. See G N Sfeir, *Modernisation of the law in Arab states*, (London. Bethesda Press, 1998), p. 54.

⁷⁰ Abdl al Ati, 'Islam in focus' pp. 195-196.

⁷¹ Nigeria Child's Rights Act, s. 215.

⁷² S O Akinwumi, 'Legal Impediments on the Practical Implementation of the Child Right Act 2003', (2009) *International Journal of Legal Information*, pp. 394 – 396.

transit to Junior Secondary Schools. Reasons for this low completion rate include economic hardship and early marriage for girls. Yet, the Act seriously frowns at same, tagging them all as an abuse of a child.

In this regard, if the purpose of government is to provide for the welfare and protection of all children, governments fail to fulfil this purpose. The state's neglect of its duties and obligations fundamentally impact on the ability of the people to lead a meaningful and dignified life. Where human survival needs frequently go unmet, protection of human rights ought to focus on 'preventing governments from neglecting their citizens.'⁷³

4.4 Legal Critique.

Nigeria operates a federal system of government in which each of the thirty-six states of the federation is autonomous and equal to the others. As a federation, the 1999 *Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria* has no reference to children specifically.⁷⁴ In fact, in the Nigerian Constitution, laws on matters pertaining to children are not listed in either the exclusive or the concurrent list, it is in the residual list, which are to be legislated on by the states' legislatures.⁷⁵ The implication is that the various states can adopt or refuse to adopt any law enacted at the national level regarding children. Since the enactment of the Nigerian Childs Rights Act 2003, which is over ten years now, only more than 20 states out of the 36 states in Nigeria have adopted the Child's Right Act into their state legislation. Giving the cultural diversity and legal pluralistic nature in Nigeria, there are various versions of state legislation on child rights, which serves as a reflection of preference of each state.⁷⁶

However, the provisions of the Child's Rights Act, 2003 supersede all other enactments on the rights of the child relating to children adoption, fostering, guardianship and wardship. Section 274 of Child rights Act specifically provides as follows:

(1) The provisions of this Act supercedes the provisions of all enactments relating to:

- a) children;*
- b) adoption, fostering, guardianship and wardship;*
- c) approved institutions, remand centres and borstal institutions; and*
- d) any other matter pertaining to children already provided for in this Act.*

⁷³ S C Agbakwa, 'Reclaiming Humanity: Economic and social and cultural rights as cornerstone of African Human rights', (2002), 5, *Yale Human Rights and development law journal*, p.177.

⁷⁴ This however does not suggest that a child in Nigeria is not entitled to enjoy the rights as enshrined under the provision of Chapter IV of the 1999 Constitution of the federal republic of Nigeria (As Amended) which contains the fundamental human rights. A child is entitled to enjoy all the rights as enshrined therein some of which include; right to life, right to fair hearing, freedom of speech, movement, association etc. See also the Nigerian Child's Rights Act, 2003, s. 3(1).

⁷⁵ Each component state under the Constitution is empowered to make laws i.e federal government makes laws on all matter in the exclusive lists and share law making with the state on the concurrent list. Children are classified for legislation under the residual matter which is legislated by the states. See the 1999 Constitution of the federal republic of Nigeria, s. 4 and 2nd Schedule, Parts I and II.

⁷⁶ See for example Kwara State Child Rights Law 2005.

(2) Accordingly, where any provision of this Act is inconsistent with that of any of the enactments specified in sub-section 1 of this section, the provision of this Act shall prevail, and that other provision shall, to the extent of its inconsistency, be void.

Perhaps, the rationale for the above provision, lies in the fact that the Act having been enacted at the national level, the states are expected to formally adopt and adapt same for domestication by the State Houses of Assembly as state laws. Therefore, State laws considered inimical to the rights of the child are to be amended or annulled as may be required, to conform to the Act. However, this rationale undermines the fact that issues of Children's rights are on the residual list of the Nigerian Constitution, and as earlier noted, which are to be legislated on by the states' legislatures.⁷⁷ In essence, the impression as could be gleaned from S.274 of the Child Rights Act, 2003 is that the Act see itself as the over-arching law, which governs all matters relating to the rights and welfare of Nigerian children, despite the cultural diversity and legal pluralistic nature in Nigeria.⁷⁸

Summarily, these section has explored a critique of the Nigerian Child Rights Act, 2003, from the cultural, religion, legal and economic points of view. As could be gleaned from the analysis therein, there are certain cultural and religious issues that affect the issues of child's rights under the Act. These include the issues of the age of who is a child, marriageable age, participation of a child in decisions making, tattoos and skin mark, adoption as well as economic prevalence in Nigeria which has grossly affected the issue of child rights, as children embark on child labour as an alternative source of income to improve the family meagre income.

It is important to state, that while this paper does not canvass that an appeal to culture or religion should excuse the violation of the fundamental rights of the Nigerian child to basic education, and all other basic needs, as well as protection against abuses, neglect, exploitation and slavery. However, the paper explores and identified these elements as among the constraints that precludes practical realisations of certain rights of the child as provided under the Act and the need to engage constructively more with 'cultural values and norms' to enhance child's rights legitimacy within the society.

5. CONCLUSION AND WAY FORWARD

Although, the Nigerian Childs Rights Act, 2003 ushered in a new dimension on the rights of children in Nigeria as it took cognizance of every person and individual affected in the care and concern with specific focus on the children and their interest in Nigeria. It specifically covers the rights to protection, participation, survival and development of the children in Nigeria. Despite these observations, it is contended that the socio cultural, religion, economic and legal pluralistic nature in Nigeria affects practical realizations of the basic rights of child under the Nigerian Child Rights Act, 2003. Considering that the level of cultural legitimacy accorded to Children's rights norms within a society, affect to a large

⁷⁷ Each component state under the Constitution is empowered to make laws. See (n.75).

⁷⁸ Considering the inconsistency of the provisions of S.274 of the Act and the Nigerian constitution, the Act at best (could and has been with substantial modification to prevalence) a model for adoption by the states legislature in Nigeria.

extent its implementation.⁷⁹ Consequently parents, society including stakeholders in Nigeria, may find it difficult abiding with the provisions of the Child Rights Act.⁸⁰ This is because the way in which Children's rights are imbibed and accepted by a society depends on how those rights are construed and fitted into the existing cultural norms and values of that society.⁸¹

There are many steps to take if certain provisions of the Act are not to continue to be a mirage in the context of a pluralized Nigeria setting. Therefore, the following ideas, among others are suggested for better and practical effectiveness:

No doubt that the Child Rights Act, 2003 remains a reviewable and amendable document. The Act thus, needs to be reviewed to encompass constructively the cultural, religious and socio economical prevalence in Nigeria. In this nexus, there is the need to identify, respect and revive some 'positive cultural and religious values' in the Nigerian societies. The family institution among others, need to be strategically helped to take the lead role in the socialization process of its members. Parents alike are to be equally guided, not only by the provisions of the Act on children's welfare, but also by observance of 'positive cultural and traditional values' in the interest of the child.

There is also the need for Government to commit funds towards improving the health, educational and social welfare of children through a stabilized national economy. Adequate financial resources to these vital institutions, if well allocated and monitored will strengthened the mechanisms for the protection and promotion of children's rights in Nigeria.

Equally, the provisions of the Child Rights Act, 2003 against child labour and the punishments (after been reviewed and amended) should be publicized widely for the purpose of deterrence. There is the need to create an awareness of child rights and how they apply to each individual in Nigeria. This can be achieved through information and awareness campaigns which are important tools in making sure that all citizens know and understand their rights. In this nexus, parents, guardians and the masses should equally be discouraged from carrying out activities that involve child labour. Children that are capable of being engaged in labour should not be engaged in labour in an excessive manner or exploited in whatever manner. Governments need to maintain a strict implementation of the Child Rights Act and adherence, especially as it regards child labour.

A consistent study and observation on the abuse of children in Nigeria should be carried out periodically. And lastly the remaining states in Nigeria that have not yet passed the Child Rights Act should do so as a matter of immediate necessity.

⁷⁹ T Kiame, 'The Convention on the Right of Child and the Cultural legitimacy of Childs Rights in Africa: some reflection', 5 *African Journal of Human Rights*. p. 223

⁸⁰ M T Ladan, member of the Expert Working Group on Children's Rights and Juvenile Justice Administration in Nigeria, quoted in: 'Amnesty International, Nigeria: The Death Penalty and Women under the Nigerian Penal System', February 2004, p.13. <<http://www.web.amnesty.org/library/print/ENGAFR440012004> > accessed on 4th of April 2015.

⁸¹ J Mason and N Bolzan *et al* "Questioning Understandings of Children's Participation: Applying a Cross-Cultural Lens." (2010) in *A Handbook of Children and Young People's Participation*, edited by B. Percy-Smith, and N. Thomas, London: Routledge 125 – 132. P. 130.